
CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS CO-OPERATIVE BANKS - A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND RESEARCH AGENDA

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Reviewing customer satisfaction with cooperative bank services is the major goal of the study. The study offers practical recommendations at the end to raise satisfaction of customers. Co-operative banks operate on the “one person, one vote” principle. Cooperative banks may offer a variety of services, including savings accounts, loans, insurance, and investment products. A board of directors is chosen by the bank's customers to direct operations and make long-term decisions.

Design: This study looks into a variety of conceptual and empirical studies on customers' satisfaction with cooperative bank services. The literature from 1996 and 2022 is reviewed in the study. The study makes use of secondary information acquired to examine consumer perception. Future, ABCD analysis is used to analyze the bank.

Findings: This research concentrated on identifying the key factors that influence customers' satisfaction with cooperative bank services. By a systematic study, it was determined that an in-depth analysis of the relationship between the various characteristics that influence how customers perceive cooperative banks is necessary in order to determine the connection between these factors.

Originality: In addition to providing principles of collaboration, peer support, democratic decision-making, and helping all elements of the community, the study highlights the possibility of customer satisfaction with cooperative banks.

Paper Type: Review Paper

Keywords: Satisfaction, Customer, Cooperative Banks, Banking, Financial, Government, Organisation, Loan, Services, ABCD Analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

A cooperative bank is owned and controlled by its members, who are often also its customers. Cooperative banks operate on the principles of cooperation and mutual assistance, with the goal of providing financial services to their members while promoting the economic and social well-being of the communities they serve. In India, cooperative banks have existed for more than a century. The Co-operative Credit Societies Act, 1904 allowed for their creation. [1]. Cooperative banks can offer a variety of services, including savings accounts, loans, insurance, and investment products. They typically operate at a local or regional level and may specialize in serving particular industries or communities. The democratic governance structure of cooperative banks is one of its distinguishing characteristics. A board of directors is chosen by the bank's customers to direct operations and make long-term decisions. Through frequent meetings and votes, members can also participate in the bank's decision-making process. The banking industry has greatly benefited the global economy [2].

In general, cooperative banks are known for their customer-centric approach and personalized service, which can lead to higher customer satisfaction levels. Cooperative Society are governed and owned by their clients, who are also their customers, and therefore they have a strong incentive to provide good service and satisfy their members' needs. The elements of the framework of the co-organizational operative include co-operation, mutual help, democratic decision making, free and open membership, and democratic decision making [3]. People with low resources frequently set up cooperative banks in order to protect themselves from the debt trap of loan companies and cooperative banks. [4]. Cooperation has two fundamental ideas that give it a distinctive strategy for addressing economic problems. exploitation and link [5]. Financial performances, a

crucial element of financial risk management, refer to the success of financial objectives. By focusing on business models that focus on retail banking and relationship banking, savings banks, and in particular cooperative banks, can foster financial inclusion for disadvantaged consumers and minimize credit throttling for small borrowers. [6]. Cooperative banks are essential to aiding the common people who lack financial support. Each bank must function efficiently and sustain its financial stability [7]. In 1904 It was decided to pass the first Co-operative Credit Societies Act. The average person can now get loans with a lower yield curve since this law permits the creation of credit organisations in urban and rural areas. [8]. Different regulations have several effects depending on the risk profile of the institutions [9]. The authors hope to provide some insight into customer service satisfaction in the Indian banking business [10].

II. OBJECTIVE

The following are the purposes of this review article:

- (1) To comprehend the broad concept of customer satisfaction and the elements that influence cooperative banks.
- (2) To identify issues concerning customer satisfaction with cooperative banks by conducting a comprehensive analysis of literature from 1996 to 2022. To arrive at ideal characteristics of customer satisfaction towards cooperative banks.
- (3) ABCD analysis will be used to investigate a cooperative bank.
- (4) To identify the research gap between the actual and desired state of studies on customer satisfaction with cooperative banking systems

III. METHODOLOGY RELATED RESEARCH WORK

Secondary data is gathered from scientific articles that have been published, bank websites, books, Google Scholar and Research Gate. To analyses advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages using ABCD analysis framework.

IV. RELATED RESEARCH WORK

4.1 CO-OPERATIVE BANKS:

Using Google Scholar and Research Gate, Table 1 below displays a systematic literature review that was conducted from 2002 to 2022 using the keywords "co-operative bank," "UCBs," and "Banking activities."

Table 1: Similar work on cooperative banks includes:

S.NO	Focus	Outcomes	References
1	As for investigate that the size of a cooperative bank influences its efficiency.	Customers approve of the instalment repayment strategy.	Gupta, J., & Jain, S. (2012) [11].
2	Outside directors have a considerable impact on efficiency measures for cooperative banks but have no discernible effect on the stock banking.	The study's findings, cooperative banks Outside director discipline is more important in stock banks, which are exposed to considerable client attention.	Yamori, N., Harimaya, k., & Tomimura, K. (2017) [12].
3	Slight financial institutions follow a consistent business plan, and their success is highly determined by the state of their local economies.	The environment has a significant impact on efficiency ratings. Banks in northeastern Italy are found to be more profitable due to a hot location, while banks in southern Italy have higher profitability, which is likely related to less	Battaglia, F., Farina, V., Fiordelisi, F., & Ricci, O. (2010) [13].

	During the efficiency measurement, the heterogeneity of environmental components must be taken into account.	intense competitive pressure .	
4	Enterprises that are co-operatively and democratically run by organised groups of people are called cooperatives.	Accordingly, cooperative corporate governance attempts to ensure the performance of the cooperative by including employees, management and members in the procedures used to develop strategy, policies and decisions.	Kamesam, V. (2002) [14].
5	The extent of cooperative banks' professional management and their democratic nature have raised the standard of general governance past a certain degree.	Identifying important differentiators for banks with exceptional governance ratings, such as fewer board members serving more than two consecutive terms and little or no presence of a family member, has served to reinforce the requirement of independence of the board of directors for effective governance.	Srivastava, D. A., & Kumar, A. (2021) [15].
6	Network configurations, business strategies, the banking relationship, the balance of members' interests, taxation, legal and regulatory frameworks are all factors in the growth and dissemination of financial cooperatives.	The economy and sustainable development, acquisitions and mergers, and bankruptcies; the advantages (and problems) of FinTech; and the value that financial cooperatives add to the real economy, especially in difficult times.	McKillop, D., French, D., Quinn, B., Sobiech, A.L. and Wilson, J.O. (2020) [16].
7	The main objectives of the Cooperative Bank "LOANS AND ADVANCES" study were to examine the bank's various loan and advance programs.	Section 5(1)(n) of the Banking Regulation Act defines an unsecured loan as "a loan or advance which is not so secured".	Haralayya, B. (2021) [17].
8	The income statement shows the net result of an organization for a given period.	Analysis of financial statements is crucial since it helps to show the financial status based on past and present facts.	Orlitzky, M., Schmidt, F.L., & Rynes, S.L. (2003) [18].
9	Analysis of financial statements is crucial since it helps to show the financial status based on past and	The estimation results demonstrate that, in comparison to their commercial counterparts, cooperative banks significantly reduce income disparities.	Minetti,R.,Murro,P.,& Peruzzi, V. (2021) [19].

	present facts.		
10	An independent group of people who have voluntarily come together to pursue their common economic, social and cultural goals through a jointly owned and democratically managed organization is called a cooperative society.	It provides agricultural funding when the public and private sectors are unable to contribute sufficiently.	Karthikeyan, K. (2021) [20].
11	City cooperative banks typically provide money to people for identities, small enterprises, home loans, and other purposes.	In order to better serve the poor, these banks must employ more women and provide opportunities for depositors and borrowers from Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes.	Khan, H. F. (2014) [21].
12	The cooperative industry has faced a number of financial challenges. Inadequate capital, cash flow issues, poor governance, a late adoption of technology, and a lack of accountability and transparency are some of the major factors that have significantly influenced how these companies operate.	The banking regulation act will be revised in 2021 to give the Reserve Bank of India more authority as part of a number of efforts the government has put in place to enhance governance and control of cooperative banking activities.	Zaman, A.U. Zaman, M.S., & Khan, N.A. (2022) [22].
13	on the Indian banks' branch networks, capital, deposits, advances, working capital, and recovery rates.	The overall financial performance of state-owned cooperative banks improved significantly during the research period on all fronts, including membership, share capital, deposits, loans and advances, reserve funds, working capital, delinquent loans and disbursed loans.	Attri, K. K., & Paul, M. (2015) [23].
14	While accepting deposits from savers and then lending the same money to borrowers looks straightforward, banking activity	Within the cooperative sector, cooperative banks are small enterprises that collaborate in both urban and rural settings.	Gupta, J., & Jain, S. (2012) [24].

	encourages the flow of money to profitable investments and purposes.		
15	To ascertain the difficulties that customers and employees face as a consequence of the absence of financial services.	Banks are unable to adopt core banking because to a lack of funding and management talent, as well as labour resistance.	Dhirubhai, A. (2013) [25].

4.2 CUSTOMER SATISFICATION:

First and foremost, we must recognise that the process of measuring customer satisfaction is not an objective act but rather an intervention that has an impact on our subsequent interactions with customers [26]. The subject has been studied from a variety of angles, with customer satisfaction surveys and customer satisfaction strategy being the most prevalent. An alternative route will be suggested. [27]. In both the public and private sectors, one of the most frequently discussed business issues is probably consumer satisfaction. [28]. The methodology enables managers to determine which factors most affect customer satisfaction and how much money should be allocated to enhancing particular factors. [29]. Customer satisfaction is achieved when an organization meets the requirements and desires of its customers. [30].

Table 2: Related works on Customer Satisfaction towards Co-operative banks:

S.NO	Contribution	References
1	According to the study, there is a strong link between customer experience and overall feelings of trust and satisfaction, which is beneficial for engaging the end user.	Sharma, M., & Chaubey, D. S. (2014) [31].
2	Every business tries to improve its customers as much as possible, because customer satisfaction is the foundation of business success. All organizations must now measure customer satisfaction. The degree of customer satisfaction is defined by the quality of the articles or the effectiveness of the customer relationship.	Ramachandran,A,& Chidambaram, V. (2012) [32].
3	There are many activities the organization can undertake to increase customer satisfaction and, therefore, retention rates. Based on available data, significant gains in customer satisfaction should result from improvements in: • service quality; • characteristics of the services; and • management of customer complaints.	Lévesque, T., & McDougall, G.H. (1996) [33].
4	Five factors can influence customer satisfaction with Internet banking: service quality, digital marketing and topic, privacy and security, simplicity of the use, and rate.	G. M., Fern, Y. S., Boon, L. K., & Huat, T.S. (2016) [34].
5	This study proposes and analyzes a model that examines the relationship between a component of service quality, namely convenience/access (or "ease of banking"), customer pleasure, customer loyalty, and customer behavior. of change, as well as customer perceptions of traditional agents and electronic financial services.	Moutinho, L., & Smith, A. (2000) [35].
6	Client retention and satisfaction are important factors in	Al-Msallam, S. (2015) [36].

	the banking industry.	
7	Customer contentment is a prerequisite for customer trust, as shown by the relationship between customer satisfaction and customer trust. Furthermore, an indirect association between customer happiness and loyalty was discovered through consumer trust. Future studies may replicate in various service contexts, and a comparison of government and private banking models will provide more information.	Leninkumar, V. (2017) [37].
8	The report analyzes how customer satisfaction levels in Indian public and private banks are affected by several aspects of service quality. By recognising the discrepancy between perceived and real service quality, customer happiness can be significantly increased.	Selvakumar, J. J. (2015) [38].
9	In order to maintain customer loyalty, retention and satisfaction, all public, private and foreign banks are now playing an important role in retail banking by offering a variety of essential banking services to all their rural and urban consumers.	Subashini, R. (2016) [39].
10	For evaluating the quality of e-services, it provides a six-dimensional scale that takes reliability, responsiveness, service availability, competence, service portfolio, and privacy into account.	Oni,A.A.,Adewoye,O.J.,& Eweoya, I. O. (2016) [40].
11	The perceived service quality dimensions identified were: Image, Responsiveness, Responsiveness, Tangibility, Reliability, Assurance, and Responsiveness. Empirical data has shown that “responsiveness” is the most important measure of customer fulfillment.	Kant, R., & Jaiswal, D. (201) [41].
12	to help banks and policy makers better understand the components of internet banking and how they impact client retention.	Firdous, S., & Farooqi, R. (2017) [42].
13	Changes occur swiftly nowadays, and it is vital for any bank to understand its clients' expectations. Customer satisfaction and the quality of the services offered are intricately related.	Rajasulochana, D., & Murthy, S. (2022) [43].
14	Satisfaction of customers with green banking initiatives' characteristics will have an effect on their overall satisfaction with the practise.	Herath,H.M.A.K.,&Herath,H.M.S.P. (2019) [44].
15	The research looks into the variables that affect patronage in the Turkish banking sector, with a particular emphasis on the effects of corporate image and reputation, as measured by patronage, service quality, and perceived value, on patronage towards Turkish banks.	Ozkan,P.,Suer,S.,Keser,I.K.,&Kocakoc, I. D. (2020) [45].
16	It was found that in order to foster customer happiness, trust, and loyalty, e-banks must prioritise service quality.	Chu, P. Y., ee, G. Y., & Chao, T. (2012) [46].
17	In the expanding IT era, a very pleased and fulfilled	Kanojia, D., & Yadav, D. R. (2012)

	customer is a wonderfully valuable non-financial product corporate banks.	[47].
18	To analyse people's attitudes towards electronic banking services in the Khammam district. To describe the current state of electronic banking in the Khammam district.	Reddy, D. K., & Reddy, M.S. (2015) [48].
19	The results showed a positive correlation between consumer satisfaction with E-banking services and information accuracy, completeness, timeliness, and relevancy. Hence, customer satisfaction affects a person's propensity to take advantage of these services.	Ayyash, M. M. (2017) [49].
20	Any bank that wants to grow and remain in business must offer excellent customer service that may create friendly relationships with clients and lead to client service.	Doddaraju, M. E. (2013) [50].

4.3 SIGNIFICANT EMPIRICAL STUDIES OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS COOPERATIVE BANKS:

Several empirical studies are being conducted by western scholars to identify the determinants to customer satisfaction towards cooperative banks.

Table 3: Shows the contribution by different authors:

S. No	Sample	Findings	References
1.	PNB and HDFC Bank, two banks with 100 responders each, are situated in the Meerut Uttar Pradesh area.	According to the analysis, there is a considerable gap in perception between Indian banks (public sector) and private sector banks regarding the general level of customer service. On the other hand, there is little distinction between private banks.	Gupta, V. P., & Agarwal, D. P. (2013) [51]
2.	160 samples using convenient sampling methods	The 5% and 1% level of significance statistical tests are performed using the fundamental statistical procedures. According to the survey, most customers choose private sector banks over public sector ones since the former prioritise building relationships with their clients and have more up-to-date infrastructure.	Virk, N., & Mahal, P. K. (2012) [52].
3.	200 respondents	The sample size for the study was one individual consumer, and the study's population is made up of bank customers. For middle-class consumers who use a bank to save their money, online and phone banking are not particularly important.	Gupta, J., & Jain, S. (2012) [53].
4.	255 samples Selected city of	The study found a significant	Sharma, M., & Chaubey,

	Uttarakhand like Dehradun, Rishikesh, Haridwar and Haldwani.	correlation between customer experience and overall emotion, trust, and contentment, which helps companies delight their customers.	D. S. (2014) [54].
5.	500 respondents Customers from both DCC and SSC Banks in Vijayapur.	Academics are interested in a survey of customer satisfaction at two cooperative banks. This study looked into how satisfied customers were with cooperative banks. These banks have different goals in mind when it comes to handling financial needs and offering other banking services.	Ganihar, N., & naikwadi, S. (2021) [55].
6.	300 respondents i.e., customer satisfaction of public and private sector	125, or 42%, of the 300 respondents indicated that they had not noticed any difference between the services offered by the banks. 97 respondents said that private sector banks offer better banking services than public sector banks. Nevertheless, 78 respondents said that public sector banks offer better financial services.	Karthikeyan, M., & kannan, K. (2021) [56].
7.	100 respondents	According to the statistics gathered, farmers and men over the age of 45 make up the majority of responders. The bulk of those holding accounts under the saving system are graduates with ordinary earnings.	Gupta, K., & Garg, I. (2022) [57].
8.	100 samples	In order for Punjab National Bank to achieve and maintain customer satisfaction in the new environment, it is important to analyse what factors are important for a successful banking relationship. We also identify and comment on the key steps we believe the bank needs to take in order to keep and grow its customer base in this competitive and increasingly sophisticated market.	Kanojia, D., & Yadav, D. R. (2012) [58].
9.	100 random samples	To investigate customer expectations for cooperative banking institutions and to measure customer satisfaction.	Maroor, J. (2013) [59].
10.	100 samples	The survey has broad and deep coverage in terms of geographic	Sequeira, A. H. (2012)

		region, number of consumers covered, and the variety and depth of information collected because the data was obtained directly from the customers.	[60].
11.	180 women respondents	The purpose of this study is to find out how satisfied Self Help Group members are with the services provided by financial institutions.	Karuppannan, R. (2012) [61].
12.	100 samples	The research concluded that attributes including reliability, responsiveness, assurance, tangibility, and empathy have an impact on consumer loyalty.	Amegayibor, G. K., & Korankye, C. O. (2021) [62].
13.	156 samples	In order to assure consistency, correctness, and uniformity, the researcher extensively evaluated the relationship between the questions and their corresponding answers. The gathered data was processed and analysed using quantitative methods.	Ndikubwimana, P., & Berndt, A. (2015) [63].
14.	225 respondents	This study offers actual proof of the advantages of a communication-oriented approach for a bank in maintaining its competitive edge in the contemporary banking system and enhancing customer satisfaction.	Cavallone, M., & Modina, M. (2013) [64]
15.	500 customers of the banks	The results of the survey show that there are significant variations between public and private sector banks in terms of the calibre of their offerings and client satisfaction.	Talukder, A. K., & Bhowal, A. (2017) [65].
16.	825 samples	According to the findings, the following subscales had the greatest impact on customer satisfaction: First, there is certainty, dependability, accessibility, and staff competencies; second, there is responsiveness and empathy; third, there is a financial component; and fourth, there is a financial component.	Pakurar, M., Haddad, H., Nagy, J., Popp, J. and Olah, J. (2019) [66].
17.	151 respondents	to examine how internet banking has affected the provision of customer service at the Nakasero	Kwarteng, P. A. (2016) [67].

		branch of Cairo Bank Uganda in the Kampala neighbourhood.	
18.	270 samples	Artificial intelligence improves the banking experience of millions of customers and employees by providing credit checks, system failure prediction, emergency alarm systems, fraud detection, web phishing detection , liquidity risk assessment, customer loyalty assessment and intelligence systems reducing the workload of employees.	Al-Araj, R.E.E.EM., Haddad, H., Shehadeh, M., Hasan, E., & Nawaiseh, M.Y. (2022) [68].
19.	125 respondents	The objective of the study is to determine the characteristics that influence the satisfaction levels of e-banking customers.	Handayani, Y. I., Agustin, H. P., & Rizqi, P. M. (2022) [69].
20.	500 samples	New private sector banks and foreign banks outperform public sector banks in the use of technology solutions.	Suguna, R., & Ravikumar, A. (2021) [70].

V. FACTORS INFLUENCING CUSTOMERS SATISFACTION TOWARDS CO-OPERATIVE BANKS

An essential issue due to the simplicity with which customers can receive this kind of service, which has boosted financial market competition and increased the requirement for building client confidence [71]. Customer happiness is crucial for your organization as it influences a variety of variables. The first influence is on the possibility that a person will become a regular customer. Customer satisfaction is also more important in the digital age because of what customers post online. Another factor that is sometimes overlooked is how much customers might spend with your business in the future.

It is critical to maintain track of a number of factors that contribute to client satisfaction, including:

(a) CLIENT UNDERSTANDING: Co-operative banks run on the basis of "one person, one vote." Since the members own these banks, a Board of Directors is elected democratically, and this group is then in charge of managing the Organization.

(b) CUSTOMER SERVICES: The primary goal of cooperative banking services is to give members of the cooperative access to credit and other financial services. Savings accounts, checking accounts, loans, mortgages, insurance, and investment services are all examples of cooperative banking services. Cooperative banks may provide a range of services, such as financial education and money management programmes, targeted at assisting members of the cooperative with their financial requirements. An indicator of product preferences and investors' propensity to continue with current items is satisfaction [72].

(c) EFFECTIVE LENDING: Instead of borrowing money for consumption or other unproductive purposes, cooperative banks promote borrowing for productive purposes. Due to this, the system has also been able to change the nature of credit.

(d) ENCOURAGING SAVINGS AND INVESTING: Rural residents can now invest and save more thanks to cooperative banking, rather of hoarding their money. Long-term advantages for the rural population's financial management will result from this.

(e) ALTERNATE CREDIT SOURCE: The rural community benefits from cooperative banking since they offer credit at a lower rate than money lenders, who often charge a higher interest rate. This shields the rural population from the money lenders' monopoly.

(f) TECHNIQUES OF FARMING IMPROVEMENT: Because of the lower interest rates on the credit supplied by cooperative banks, the rural populace may now use it for improved farming methods such as purchasing seeds, chemical fertilisers, and so on. This has also allowed them to market their products at competitive costs.

VI. ABCD LISTING OF COOPERATIVE BANKS

The Advantages, Benefits, Constraints and Disadvantages (ABCD) of a system can be used to effectively review and understand the model/system [73]. Influencing factors and critical components of components based on the key attributes of many defining issues of a concept, business model, strategy or system, categorized into four concepts: benefits, advantages, limitations and disadvantages [74]. ABCD Assessment A model is a simple yet organized analysis tool for business or operating models, systems, concepts, ideas, plans, technologies, and strategic analysis that can be used as an assessment technique. primary analysis in a variety of fields or sectors. [75]. Using elemental analysis technique, analyze the significant constituent element discovered for each ABCD construct [76]. Several research are now using the ABCD analysis framework, a well-known technique for analysing a business proposition [77]. It is possible to create a full list of these elements and zero in on the important underlying determinant problems that are most likely to rule the model using the ABCD analysis framework as a guide. Once a large number of issues have been selected for consideration, a qualitative technique can be used to construct a list of the main advantages, limitations and disadvantages for each defining issue identified. [78]. ABCD analysis delves into the difficulties by examining them from numerous stakeholder perspectives, providing deeper insights into the concept, system, business, or strategy [79]. It investigates the individual qualities, system features, and the effectiveness of an idea or approach [80].

ADVANTAGES:

- (a) Cooperative banks have helped the rural populace by offering credit and loans at rates that are lower than those demanded by local money lenders.
- (b) They are well-known throughout the nation and have succeeded in keeping a close relationship with their clients.
- (c) Creating a good customer practise password in banking services takes time [81].
- (d) Inspires customers to maintainable behaviour [82].

BENEFITS:

- (a) Since their main objective is to provide excellent services to their members rather than making a profit, cooperative banks offer loans to their customers at significantly reduced interest rates.
- (b) Producers' savings habits have also been instilled through cooperative banks, which have encouraged saves and investment.
- (c) Public sector banks, private sector banks, regional rural banks, small financial banks, NBFCs, microfinance institutions and cooperative banks in rural and urban areas spread financing needs [83].
- (d) Customer satisfaction is an indicator of the quality of services provided to customers [84].

CONSTRAINTS:

- (a) One of the causes is a lack of sufficient training and instruction for members in cooperative principles and operations.
- (b) The operation of a cooperative society is strictly governed by the laws and regulations established by the government.
- (c) As this is a new field, there is little standardization [85].
- (d) Customers perceive no difference in the financial products given by service-oriented banks because every new item is soon matched by competitors [86].
- (e) Banks can improve their competitiveness by delivering exceptional customer service [87].

DISADVANTAGES:

- (a) A few of them have stopped giving credits and money to the rural people due to a shortage of investors and funding.
- (b) The growth of cooperative banks is not uniform across the nation. While some states have lost units, others have more useful and effective ones.
- (c) Boundaries on share capital [88].

(d) The investment based on their experience and on circulars and instructions published by the RBI from time to time [89].

(e) Customers' expectations in different regions differ from one another, it can be mentioned [90].

VII. RESEARCH GAP

(a) The functions of the cooperative society parents and other regulating body if any on company success and the organization [91]. The review of literature states there is a scope for further study to determine the success of cooperative bank based on factors such as capital formation, capital and transformation.

(b) Future research can be carried to investigate potential distinctions between different bank types, such as the function of relational trust in commercial banks as opposed to cooperative banks, in order to draw even more significant conclusions [92].

(c) The study aims to determine whether rural co-operative banks in Uttarakhand, India, are meeting the needs of the rural populace by assessing customer satisfaction [93]. Few minor studies have pointed determinates to customer satisfaction; however, major studies are limited. Therefore, there is a need for important affecting factor to customer satisfaction.

(d) The most important factor affecting customer loyalty is the relationship between a bank and its clients [94].

(e) The problem exists, society has a difficult time assessing the true value of loans made to borrowers who have diverted their funds to other activities or consumer needs [95]. Further, the study can also consider the problems encountered by the customer while applying for loan facility through cooperative banks.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In India, cooperative banks are involved in banking, production, processing, and marketing [96]. The banking sector is crucial to accelerating the nation's economic growth by encouraging residents to save, supporting company financial needs, and increasing the rate of capital formation. It was believed that cooperatives would be crucial in bringing about socioeconomic change [97]. It seems to have consumers, how much they spend, and how frequently they buy. The average loan amount from commercial banks was more than that from cooperative banks [98]. Satisfied consumers will come back, buy more, and contact the bank frequently for a variety of reasons. One could say that the profitability positions of these institutions need to be improved [99]. The increase in deposits was made possible by the increase in the number of members [100]. The banking sector is crucial to accelerating the nation's economic growth by encouraging residents to save, supporting company financial needs, and increasing the rate of capital formation. The quality of e-banking services is critical in e-banking research because e-banking increases organizational profitability and consumer engagement and loyalty. [101]. A bank's existence, growth, and longevity are entirely dependent on its customers. Customer service has long been an important concern for banks. Consumers have a significant impact on the perception of the quality of service provided by banks. Banks should use current banking methods such as internet banking, credit cards, ATMs, etc. Cooperative Banks should devise new strategies for recruiting new consumers and delighting existing ones. Banks should strengthen their customer service to a greater extent.

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